

A network diagram with various sized blue and grey nodes connected by thin lines, forming a complex web structure on the left side of the page.

Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Final version

D7.4

April 2024

Co-funded by the European Union under project ID 101076349. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project Data	
Project Acronym	ENERGATE
Project Name	Energy Efficiency Aggregation Platform for Sustainable Investments
Grant Agreement Nr.	101076349
Project Coordinator	National Technical University of Athens
Project Duration	1 January 2023 – 30 June 2025
Website	https://www.energate-project.eu

Deliverable Data	
Deliverable No	D7.4
Dissemination Level	Public
Work Package	WP7
Lead Beneficiary	REHVA
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Due Date	30.04.2024
Release Date	30.04.2024

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Published in April 2024 by ENERGATE.

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Acknowledgments:

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Executive Summary

This deliverable represents the 2nd and final release of the communication and dissemination strategy for the ENERGATE project. Since this represents an update of the strategy, certain chapters have remained untouched and continue to be implemented in the current strategy. The project has remained consistent with its identity, and while it advances, there have been some additions and minor changes, but the overall principles remain unchanged. Thus, most chapters haven't changed since D7.1. The core structure of the deliverable has also remained the same to ensure continuity and provide greater clarity for observing the changes that have taken place. The status of all project communication and dissemination activities has been reported and evaluated in D7.2 and therefore, won't be addressed in this deliverable.

Currently the strategy is close to its second phase, described in D7.1(**Phase II – Enhance acceptance of ENERGATE ICT-enabled solution and promoting the ENERGATE platform (M18-Y3)**), the focus will be to engage with the target audience identified in phase I and to introduce it to the ENERGATE platform in close collaboration with WP5 (stakeholder engagement and ecosystem reinforcing activities).

The key activities to be conducted during Phase II include publications about project results, the organisation of conferences, events, workshops, and participatory activities (e.g., labs) promoting knowledge exchange.

In this phase, ENERGATE will engage the target stakeholders at the national level, especially through the organisation of regional workshops and webinars in the partners' countries and in their national language, and at the EU level through the organisation of a final event in Brussels. The event will aim to link the projects' results with EU policy discussions and bring together high-level representatives from different organisations and institutions.

1. Introduction

It is common that the terms “communication” and “dissemination” are used interchangeably regarding promotion activities. This is neither entirely false nor entirely correct. Although communication and dissemination have indeed a lot in common, there are certain points which significantly differentiate them. As a starting point, communication and dissemination are both important as their main goal is to promote the project leading to awareness raising and increased interest, and finally enabling the project to make an impact. However, these two terms are different regarding the specific goal of promotion and the respective audience.

In particular, **communication** relates to the promotion of the project to general public in order to show the impact and benefits that it achieved, focusing on both the project and its results. On the other hand, **dissemination's** objective is to transfer the knowledge and results gained within the project to these specific audiences that are most probable to use them, focusing on the description and availability of the project's results.

Dissemination and communication are horizontal activities and concentrate on distributing the activities and results of ENERGate itself to a wide range of existing or potential stakeholders, belonging to different target groups. The dissemination activities are aimed at achieving different goals, towards different targets, in different phases of a project, having (phase by phase) different material available. Communication of ENERGate results is taking several forms and using a variety of tools. Some tools have a greater impact than others, and thus, their value to the aims of the project may differ.

1.1. Deliverable Overview

This deliverable evaluates and updates the plan to ensure targeted events and channels are still valid. In Chapter 2, the ENERGate target groups are defined as well as the main project's stakeholders in liaison with WP5 (T.5.1 Stakeholder mapping and engagement). This serves as a plan and is linked to the following sections in which the process of the Visual Identity creation is introduced (Chapter 3) followed by the ENERGate communication channels that have been put in place and serve as a main dissemination tool for the project (Chapter 4). In Chapter 5 the ENERGate Communication and Promotional Package is presented. Chapter 6 outlines the Scientific Publications and the target fixed. Chapter 7 focuses on the events ENERGate is targeting that have been categorized and are strictly linked to the target group identified in Chapter 2. Chapter 8 outlines the Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters' activities. Furthermore, Chapter 9 introduces the reporting methodology (KPIs and monitoring) of the communications activities. To conclude, Chapter 10 outlines an updated non-exhaustive list of activities planned for the second half of ENERGate implementation (M16-M30).

1.2. Deliverable Objectives

The aim of this deliverable is to review the tailored strategy established at the beginning of the project and plan the next dissemination and communication activities with a view to effectively conveying the key messages of ENERGate to its target audiences as well as increasing the visibility of the project along with its activities and results, thus paving the road for a potential post-project deployment and uptake.

The communication and dissemination plan has been elaborated at the project start, listing objectives and messages, target groups and how to reach them, resources (tools, HR, time

and budget), KPIs and evaluation mechanisms, risks and challenges as well as modus operandi. The plan lists different channels to reach the several target groups, such as preferred communication methods, a social media pack for partners, relevant conferences and raise interest, identification of relevant media channels and synergies that could be created with other EU projects or networks. It also includes the project identity and basic promotional package.

2. Review of the Stakeholder Management Plan (SMP):

As in D7.1, the mapping of the main target groups of the project is listed below and serves both WP5 and WP7. Each target group is approached by communication and dissemination activities that focus on the benefits they can accrue from the project and targeted channels. WP7 lists the engagement and dissemination activities and the communication material that will be used. All activities are described in [D7.2 Monitoring of Dissemination Activities and Communication Material](#) more in detail.

Overall, target stakeholders are divided into three hierarchical levels: those in the first level are key users and beneficiaries of the ENERGATE platform; those in the second level may use the ENERGATE platform as a source of information to support their activities, though they are not key users; and those in the third level are not expected to become users of the ENERGATE platform, despite being potentially useful as amplifiers of the project's messages.

After mapping all stakeholders, key messages were designed for each segment, based on their potential interest in the ENERGATE platform, as identified for WP5. These key messages have been slightly modified in comparison with D7.1 and are now closer to the interests and needs expressed by stakeholders during their first interactions with the ENERGATE consortium. The messages guide the execution of all communication and dissemination activities, thus improving their impact and efficacy in promoting the adoption of the tool. They also support the execution of the engagement strategy laid out in *D5.1 Stakeholder engagement plan with consultation guide*.

Table 1: Stakeholder mapping and plan

Level	Segment	Subsegment	Key message	Key channels
First	Financial Stakeholders	Private financing bodies (private)	Partner with top-tier renovation projects and optimise your investment strategy on ENERGATE, where the right match leads to impactful returns.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events • Website • Newsletter • Communication collaterals (infographics, briefs, non-scientific articles...)
		Public financing bodies (public)	It's easier to identify the most attractive bundle to get the desired impact in energy efficiency projects.	
		Fund managers	ENERGATE streamlines your search for viable investments, providing a curated selection of projects with high-yield potential.	
		Investment consultants	You can better define interesting investment opportunities by comparing attractive "bundles" of projects.	
		Private investors	You can access information about the projects, conduct Due Diligence and provide financial support	
		Banks	Uncover and finance projects that align with your institution's investment criteria, driving forward sustainable development	
First	Building Stakeholders	ESCOs	Utilise ENERGATE to showcase your projects to a network of building owners and financiers, setting a new benchmark for collaboration and success in the industry.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events • Website • Newsletters • Mainstream Media • Social Media • Communication collaterals (infographics, briefs, non-scientific articles...)
		Project developers	Utilise ENERGATE to showcase your projects to a network of building owners and financiers, setting a new benchmark for collaboration and success in the industry.	
		Building owners	Gain insights into your building's performance, connect with renovation experts, and access innovative financing options.	
		Asset managers	Employ ENERGATE to benchmark and enhance your assets while engaging with a community of	

Level	Segment	Subsegment	Key message	Key channels
			implementors and investors focused on value creation.	
Second	Policy makers and policy support	Policy makers	Rely on ENERGate for comprehensive data and collaborative insights that inform sustainable policy creation and building regulations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletters • Events • Website • Communication collaterals (infographics, briefs, non-scientific articles...)
		Policy support organisations	You can access to accurate and centralised information on funded EE projects, funding opportunities, and achieved outcomes.	
Second	Research institutes and universities		The ENERGate research and results can provide inputs to your own research.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conferences • Scientific Publications • Events • Social Media • Website
Third	Others	NGO	Find collaborators and financial allies on ENERGate to elevate your energy efficiency projects and amplify your environmental impact.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication collaterals (infographics, briefs, non-scientific articles...) • Website • Mainstream Media • Social Media
		Media	N/A	
		General public	N/A	
		Technical Chambers	You can learn from case studies about the demands of financial stakeholders.	
		Energy Associations	You can find funding opportunities for your projects and learn from case studies.	
		Real Estate	You can find funding opportunities for your projects and learn from case studies.	

3. Visual Identity & Resources

Creating a common project's visual identity is key to raising awareness and interest regarding ENERGATE's future activities and outcomes. From the first month of the project, the consortium worked and collaborated in the process of making a strong project identity.

This visual identity package includes the following items:

- Project logo and colours
- Typeface
- Banners for project website, email signature and social media profile (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook)
- Newsletter cover
- Brand identity manual
- Deliverable (docx) and presentation (pptx) templates
- Greeting cards
- Poster – Banner
- Factsheets and briefs
- User Profiles

All the material is available on the [Teams repository](#). Below you can find details of most visual identity items.

3.1. ENERGATE Logo

During the kick-off meeting, held in Athens in January, partners were asked to vote and provide inputs on the ENERGATE logo propositions and the ENERGATE colour palette. Eight different logo options have been presented and voted on using a Google form (<https://forms.gle/sEqKaVnWnkdmLYi6>).

More details about the logo proposition and the logo selections process are given in ANNEX I of this deliverable.

Figure 1: ENERGATE logo selection

Figure 2: ENERGATE logo v. 1

Logo Construction

Figure 3: ENERGATE logo construction

In addition, four colours' variations of the logo have been created, to be used in the different communication channels and in all ENERGATE documents (Deliverables, presentations, events agenda etc.).

Figure 4: ENERGATE logo colours variation

3.1.1. ENERGATE Brand Manual

To create a common visual identity, it is essential to aggregate all the information in one document that sets the rules to follow for the whole consortium. Following this purpose, ENERGATE has created its own brand manual that sets the basis for all communication and dissemination activities and products. The brand manual is articulated in four main sections:

- Verbal Identity
- Logo Guidelines
- Typography
- Colours

The brand manual has been published on the project repository and is accessible to all partners. All partners will have to follow the guidelines set in the brand manual for the overall duration of the project.

Words

Logo Colors

Hex: #1683C8
R: 22
G: 131
B: 200

Hex: #305C83
R: 48
G: 92
B: 131

Hex: #000000
R: 00
G: 00
B: 00

Figure 5: ENERGATE brand manual

3.2. ENERGATE Templates

As part of the ENERGATE Visual Identity, a Word template has been developed for ENERGATE which can be used both for formal deliverables as well as for (other) formal documents for the projects (events' agendas, minutes from General Assemblies etc.). Similarly, a PowerPoint template has been developed as well to ensure a common identity at events. All templates are available in the project repository and are being used for internal and external communication.

The prior templates underwent modification following changes in the consortium partners. The revised versions no longer include the Engineering logo. In addition, the YouTube logo has been added with redirection to the ENERGATE channel.

Figure 6: ENERGATE deliverable template

Figure 7: ENERGate PowerPoint Template

Figure 8: ENERGATE agenda template

In addition, two different banners have been created for ENERGATE:

- Newsletter banner
- Social media banner

Figure 9: ENERGate Newsletter & Social Media banner

Figure 10: ENERGate Banner for reports

4. ENERGATE Digital Outreach

Several project-related tools will be leveraged to communicate about the project digitally: a website, newsletters, social media and the use of platforms as multipliers. The update in this section relates to the dates of the two phases. Phase I has been extended until M18 and will include the testing phase of the platform. Phase II will officially start in M19 with the public release of the platform.

Table 2: ENERGATE Digital Outreach plan

Mechanism	Phase I: Raise awareness/interest among key stakeholders (M1-M18)	Phase II: Enhance acceptance of ENERGATE ICT-enabled solution and promoting the ENERGATE platform (M19-M30):
Project Website	I) Design & Development of an intuitive and responsive project's website. Promotion of objectives and project scope.	II) Regular update of the website content with news, events and results; Watch the website's analytics to measure impact and provide content of interest. Promote the platform website, guidelines and benefits for users.
Social Media Campaign	I) Establishment of presence in Social Media Reproduce relevant content & monitor relevant hashtags; Upload public material; Follow influencers of the domain; Engage with other projects and initiatives.	II) Promote the project's outcomes, the platform, and events; Interact with followers to get feedback; Answer comments and private messages on the various channels; Upload public material; Reproduce relevant content and monitor relevant hashtags. Strong cooperation with the #SmartEnergyCluster and relevant projects
Newsletters	I) Newsletter to announce the project's launch and the website, events and public results (reports, survey, factsheets, infographic, scientific papers), prepare the ground for the platform dissemination,	II) Newsletter to announce the significant events/results and platform release.

4.1. Website

The ENERGATE website (energate-project.eu) development is of significant importance for the effective promotion of the ENERGATE action, as it will contribute to target groups' awareness raising and it will create interest and attract potential contributions to the whole effort. Moreover, the website content has been vastly explained in D7.2 (section 2.2.1).

The project website aims to:

- Ensure open access to project public results;
- Support the exploitation: results will be available for 2 years after the project's end;
- Increase the visibility of the ENERGATE platform and its features.

The website is now fully operating and includes basic project information, such as title, logo, brief description, objectives, methodology (ENERGATE Approach “Fetch-Process-Deliver”), work structure, expected contribution, and consortium. Moreover, the website contains information on the events organised by the project, as well as the events in which ENERGATE partners have participated in (external events). In addition, the website ensures open access to (public) project results easily and freely.

The website approach continues to rely on more digestible descriptions about ENERGATE activities and avoids typical “project language” (e.g. deliverables, outputs, etc.), talking rather about objectives, successes, services, etc. A dedicated ENERGATE page has been created on the websites of all consortium partners (see section 2.2.1 of D7.2).

The website contains the following items:

- Information about the project, including Objectives, Methodology, Contribution, Participants etc.;
- News and Events with relative information such as agendas, photos, events’ scope, etc.;
- Library with main outputs, deliverables, reports, scientific publications, articles;
- Communication resources (brochure, newsletters, infographics, newsletters, synergies with relevant projects etc).

Figure 11: Current ENERGATE website structure

The website and electronic communication practices are compliant with the current EU legislation on personal data and communications - General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Compliance with GDPR is ensured in the case of third-party tools used in managing electronic dissemination via the web, such as website traffic analytics, embedded multimedia, electronic communications’ automation tools and other functionalities.

The ENERGATE dissemination strategy foresees two milestones regarding the website's traffic, in order to ensure and tangibly display the success of the dissemination activities and promotion of the project. For this purpose, the *Google Analytics* (GA) service will be added, to track in detail the visitor traffic of the ENERGATE website. GA offers detailed statistics about the website's traffic and the traffic

sources. It will also provide information regarding the number of ENERGATE website visitors, as well as the percentage of new visitors, the number of visits and pageviews, allowing to monitor the website's success as a means of dissemination and information provision. It is foreseen that the ENERGATE website will attract at least 5,000 unique visitors and 15% return visitors. Finally, the website will also support the project's exploitation strategy for at least 2 years after its completion.

The official launch of the website was done in M5 – May 2023.

4.2. Social Media identity

Social media, particularly Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube have become platforms that are easily accessible to anyone with internet access. Increased communication for organisations fosters brand awareness. Additionally, social media serve as a relatively inexpensive platform for organisations to implement marketing campaigns and effectively disseminate outcomes and associated information. With the proliferation of niche sites and communities on the Internet, it is becoming increasingly important to target long tail search terms and cast a wide net.

In this framework, exploiting all the assets social media have to offer, while considering the related risks, could be truly beneficial in successfully disseminating the ENERGATE scope, activities and outcomes. Through social networking, ENERGATE is gaining wide access to the power of web publishing to non-technical users cost-effectively, while e.g. LinkedIn, Twitter users drive traffic to ENERGATE website, articles, workshops, etc.

Links to ENERGATE social media accounts are added to all the pages of the ENERGATE website.

Posts and tweets include announcements for events, reports and publications, dissemination activities, new dissemination material, several achievements, and results. Photos are also uploaded from ENERGATE events and interventions in conferences.

ENERGATE adapts different strategies according to the social media channels. For [Twitter](https://twitter.com/Energate_eu)¹, due to the 250-character limit per post, it's essential to focus on very specific aspects, depending on the topic. For events, including the type and title of the event, the date, and the link, along with a banner, is being promoted. For other dissemination and communication activities, we always include the key points to ensure the audience is well-informed. For [LinkedIn](https://www.linkedin.com/company/energate-project)², as more text fits, more details are included because the platform's audience is more likely to follow as well. A banner is recommended, and links to the dissemination and communication activities are provided. Last but not least, for Youtube³, a strategy for showing the User Interface of the ENERGATEs' upcoming platform was prepared, featuring four

¹ https://twitter.com/Energate_eu

² <https://www.linkedin.com/company/energate-project>

³ https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCJt6_aeEq-9KzQ8W4UQ79Gw

distinct videos that showcase the user interfaces tailored to different stakeholders: Building Owners, Implementors, Financiers, and Public Bodies. Moving forward, we plan to create an introductory video about ENERGATE. This video will be designed to reach a broader audience, allowing more people to learn about the project and its benefits.

Figure 12: ENERGATE Social Media

Figure 13: ENERGATE top LinkedIn posts

Figure 14. ENEREGATE top Twitter posts

Figure 15: ENEREGATE youtube account

Campaigns, including hashtags and posts, are regularly shared with partners via email to ensure consistency and track performance and mentions, so they can directly click and share. In such campaigns, target stakeholders such as relevant national and local organisation, policy makers, NGOs are tried to be tagged when relevant. In order to be able to track the project

posts and mentions, every social media posts will have to include the project hashtag [#energate_eu](#). Of course, The Dissemination Leader, with the support of the project partners, has already identified and is actively following the accounts of relevant EU projects. In addition, hashtags such as LIFEprogramme and #LIFEproject have helped to disseminate our activities, while on Twitter hashtags such as @LIFEprogramme and @cleanenergy_eu were used to link the project to other clean energy projects. Other hashtags used include: #LIFEprogramme, #LIFEproject, #LIFEprojects, #LIFEAmplifier. ENERGATE proudly aligns with the initiatives of the Smart Energy Cluster, fostering a partnership that underscores our commitment to innovation and sustainability in the energy sector. This collaboration along with 21 EU projects, not only amplifies our capabilities but also enables us to share knowledge, resources, and best practices, thereby enhancing our overall impact.

Through active engagement in the Smart Energy Cluster, we have participated in numerous joint ventures and cross-promotional activities that demonstrate our dedication to advancing smart energy solutions. By leveraging the strengths of our partnership and utilising the #SmartEnergyCluster hashtag, we have successfully increased our visibility and influence.

The number of posts, campaigns and content is being designed according to the different development of the project, focusing more on the share of the ongoing activities, events, public deliverables and shared results from the platform and the pilots. Each post includes the specific thematic hashtag and reference and tag to the key partners. The content is produced in order for partners to post independently on their social media channel. To guarantee the outreach to the main target audience, the partners are welcomed to translate the content into their national language.

EPU NTUA's and other partners' existing accounts are used to disseminate information on a regular basis and engage with target groups. Where possible, followers are being re-directed to the website to boost traffic. A **shared Excel table of target accounts** to follow or tag is available in the Teams shared folder. All partners are regularly asked to fill it in with key actors at national and local levels.

In our ongoing efforts to enhance our digital presence and understand the behavior and preferences of our audience, we employ Google Analytics as a pivotal tool in our website management strategy, through our dissemination and communication monitoring tool. This service provides comprehensive insights into user interactions on our website, allowing us to tailor our content and user experience to better meet the needs of our visitors.

For instance, data from Google Analytics helps us track metrics such as the number of users, new users, returning users, and specific interactions like event triggers, publication views, news and events views, and newsletter engagement. Our data indicates an encouraging percentage of returning users, suggesting a growing interest and sustained engagement with our content.

Moreover, through detailed event tracking, we have been able to monitor the impact of specific content types, such as communication materials, which are essential for our outreach and dissemination activities. This analytical approach not only informs our strategic decisions but also supports our objective of continuously improving user engagement and outreach effectiveness.

4.3. Newsletters

All e-newsletters are released in electronic format through the [mailerlite](https://www.mailerlite.com/)⁴ platform, in order to promote the project and its events as well as to disseminate ENEREGATE outcomes. The e-Newsletter is disseminated to relevant stakeholders at EU and MS level who have already subscribed and have provided their consent to receive electronic communications regarding ENEREGATE progress, according to GDPR. Of course, all the newsletters are shared among partners networks, social media, newsletters, websites.

Newsletters are now available on the project website⁵. A newsletter template which follows the project visual design was created. The [first newsletter](#) disseminated the project general information and the kick-off meeting, the website and upcoming events, while the [second newsletter](#) focused on SmartEnergyCluster initiative. Both were released after M5 – May 2023, after the finalisation and publication of the website. The content of the e-Newsletters is drafted by NTUA in collaboration with partners.

Additionally, targeted invitations for events or other campaigns and press releases have been distributed, meeting the expected Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and contributing to unanticipated communications actions that have enhanced the overall strategy.

All partners (if applicable) add content in their individual newsletters related to project activities, events, report, etc. The release of ENEREGATE newsletters is well on track for the achievement of the KPI. However, it is worthy of note that in this area, too, partners are active. The project has been featured in 9 newsletters of consortium partners, thus expanding its impact beyond forecasts.

While the KPI for this segment will stay the same (5 newsletters), an additional stretch goal of at least 2 more references in external newsletters will be added.

⁴ <https://www.mailerlite.com/>

⁵ <https://energate-project.eu/>

5. ENERGATE Communication and Promotional Package

To kickstart the communication of ENERGATE, a promotional package has been developed and shared with all the consortium partners. This package includes a poster and a brochure that should support partners with pitching the project to relevant stakeholders. Moreover, the communication and promotional package now counts with a complementary slide deck with key project information, an official roll up for events, the ENERGATE one pager, the factsheets for our different platform users and specific infographics with highlights from our events.

As mentioned in D7.2, the 'communication material' offers a collection of promotional and informational resources that not only include the figures bellowed mentioned but also other factsheets and infographics detailing financing typologies for building renovation, use cases for the Energy Efficiency Marketplaces, takeaways from training workshops, and expert talks like the REHVA Brussels Summit. All this material can be found [on the website](#).

The target for infographics and fact sheets – the production of assets inspired by the reports of WP2 – was achieved with the development of 3 assets. However, as more outputs are expected to be released until the end of the project, this strategy will continue active. A stretch goal of 3 more assets will be considered for the rest of the project.

With regards to printing materials, partners are encouraged to prioritise the digital distribution of project communication materials in order to avoid waste. Additionally, an increased effort in digital dissemination will serve as mitigation strategy.

Regarding the distribution of printed brochures partners are encouraged to prioritise the digital distribution of project communication materials to actively avoid creating waste. Additionally, an increased effort in digital dissemination will serve as mitigation strategy, if the expected numbers are not reached.

The different formats of the resources in the promotional package should cover all the common situations where project information is needed; however, additional resources may be added if the consortium agrees on their relevance.

The promotional package is available online to all partners for the whole duration of the project. It is worth noting that, it is being constantly updated based on the needs of each activity and the changes that may occur in the project.

Where energy services meet sustainable finance

The ENERGATE marketplace is an ICT-based platform which, on the one hand, aims to mobilise and accelerate the creation of NECP-compatible credible project pipeline, and, on the other, aims to facilitate the financial closure and project implementation by offering standardisation, risk mitigation and appropriate "packaging" of investments.

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Co-funded by the European Union under project ID 101070240. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or ENEC. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Building renovation investments made easy, predictable, and risk-weighted

- Large and standardised project development facility
- Asset bundling scaled investment
- Feedback loops to measure the impact of the platform
- Matching opportunities with investors
- Business matchmaking, quality assessments, and rankings

How?

STAGE 1 | FETCH
Collect information on building renovation projects in a structured manner. Ensure that key technical and commercial information is properly declared. Users will also select their preferred financing methods and compare performance KPIs.

STAGE 2 | PROCESS
Identification of similarities between projects and investors KPIs which might result in bundles. ENERGATE enables the best combination of projects and project financing based on KPIs, and financial indicators provided.

STAGE 3 | DELIVER
Follow up on projects, continuous feeding of the database, validation of M&V methodologies, and definition of relevant KPIs and benchmarks. Development of a user profile management functionality.

Expected impact

- 5 PILOTS PARTNERS IN 6 EU COUNTRIES
- UP TO 180 BUILDING RENOVATION PROJECTS
- UP TO 132 FINAL ENERGY SAVINGS GWh/year
- UP TO 171 GHG EMISSIONS SAVED tCO₂e/year
- UP TO 314 TRIGGERED INVESTMENTS Million Euros

EPU, IEECP, flexiwatt, emerbain, SUSTAINABLE CITY, GreenSenseCapital, GREENESCO, commutty, ILOK CONSULTANTS

Figure 15: ENERGATE brochure

ENERGATE
ENERGY EFFICIENCY MARKETPLACE

Building renovation investments: easy, predictable, and risk-weighted

- Large and standardised project development facility
- Asset bundling scaled investment
- Feedback loops to measure the impact of the platform
- Matching opportunities with investors
- Business matchmaking, quality assessments, and rankings

How?

STAGE 1 | FETCH
Collect structured information about projects. Ensuring that technical and commercial data is appropriate.

STAGE 2 | PROCESS
Identification of similarities between projects and investors KPIs which might result in bundles.

STAGE 3 | DELIVER
Follow up on projects, validation of M&V methodologies, and definition of relevant KPIs.

Expected impact

- 5 PILOTS PARTNERS IN 6 EU COUNTRIES
- UP TO 180 BUILDING RENOVATION PROJECTS
- UP TO 132 FINAL ENERGY SAVINGS GWh/year
- UP TO 171 GHG EMISSIONS SAVED tCO₂e/year
- UP TO 314 TRIGGERED INVESTMENTS Million Euros

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EPU, IEECP, flexiwatt, emerbain, SUSTAINABLE CITY, GreenSenseCapital, GREENESCO, commutty, ILOK CONSULTANTS

Figure 16: ENERGATE poster

Where energy services meet sustainable finance

A marketplace to facilitate the financial closure and implementation of energy efficiency projects in buildings.

- Standardised facility
- Feedback loops
- Project aggregation
- Business matchmaking

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Figure 17. ENERGATE Roll up

6. Scientific Publications

It is important that key results of ENERGATE are made available to the larger possible stakeholder group to ensure ownership and the scientific community is one of the project target groups. These activities include a number of scientific articles and concrete actions to facilitate the interaction/synergies with stakeholders from other related to ENERGATE projects and initiatives.

The target set for this segment is still in progress, as for the KPI: *at least 2 papers need to be submitted to scientific journals or to a Special Issue and at least 2 conference papers.* ENERGATE has by now achieved 4 conference paper submissions, 3 in progress, and 2 journal paper in progress. The scientific publications analytical list can be found in the D7.2 “Monitoring of Dissemination Activities and Communication Material”, Annex IX| Scientific Publications [here](#).

Partners will be regularly reminded of the target KPI for scientific publications and encouraged to achieve it during consortium meetings and other direct interactions.

7. Events

The event activities are linked to the dissemination of the project results through conferences and workshops organised externally or by the project consortium. The next paragraphs will dive deep into the different activities related to events. Once more, all the events participation and organisation are listed on D7.2. The paragraphs below give an overview of the strategy taken by the project.

7.1. Project-branded events

The ENERGATE partners are encouraged to organize online and offline events whenever they have relevant messages and results to showcase. These events may be organised autonomously or under the umbrella of bigger events (such as the European Sustainable Energy Week).

All pilot partners should organise 2 webinars, so a total of 10 webinars by the end of the project. Moreover, the project will host one webinar to present the ENERGATE platform (when a demo version is ready for release) and one final event to present the results of the project. Additionally, four regional training workshops (in Latvia, Spain, Italy, and Hungary) are being planned, although participation may be restricted if the local partner so decides. Up until now, the Spanish workshop has been successfully organised in September 2023 in Madrid. A [factsheet](#) has been developed to present the key takeaways of the event, while an [article](#) was published to provide a comprehensive look at the ENERGATE Workshop through survey insights. The Latvian workshop is being organised in May 2024.

7.2. External Events

External events can be categorised two-fold: events organised by other research projects; and events organised by European or national-level institutions.

7.2.1. Events organised by other projects

Being part of events organised by other projects allows ENERGATE to broaden its reach and increase visibility, as some relevant stakeholders might not have been reached yet by the project activities but follow other projects. Moreover, such events promote knowledge exchange and cooperation between consortia, bridging results and giving space to mutual inputs.

Currently ENERGATE participated in 4 events organised by other projects:

- [BIGG Final event](#)
- [3rd Greek SMAFIN Roundtable](#)
- [ENERGATE and EN-TRACK Webinar](#): Innovative Pathways for Enhanced Building Renovations
- Upcoming: [From Tech to Transformation: Accelerating Building Energy Efficiency through ICT Solutions](#) (Joint Initiative with InEEExS and FORTESIE)

All these activities will be analysed in detail in *D6.5 Joint activities with other projects and initiatives v1*.

7.2.2. Events organised by other institutions

When ENERGATE takes part in external events that are organized outside the scope of EU-funded research projects, project reach also goes beyond the limits of the research world. In the specific case of this project, such visibility has a high impact, as the ENERGATE platform is being designed to serve users that are not researchers nor policymakers.

All partners of ENERGATE are encouraged to participate in external events, so that the project is featured in such activities at least twice a year.

Considering the project's target stakeholders and objectives, a preliminary list of external events has been built as seen below. However, this list should be regarded as a reference and, simultaneously, as a living document: not only are these events not mandatory, but they are also not exclusive. The list should be completed throughout the project, following inputs and suggestions from all partners.

ENERGATE up to M16 has participated in the following 'external' events:

- [REHVA Brussels Summit](#), 13-14th of November 2023, Brussels, Belgium.
- [Global Green Growth Week 2023](#), 23-27th of October 2023, Budapest, Hungary.
- [14th International Conference on Information Intelligence Systems and Applications 2023 \(IISA\)](#), 10-12th of July, Volos, Greece.
- [9th International Symposium and 31st National Conference on Operational Research](#), 29-30th of June & 1st of July 2023, Athens, Greece.
- [Workshop held at Riga City Council](#), 6th of April 2023, Riga, Latvia.

Table 3: ENERGATE target events *Event*

ENERGATE target events	Target audience
Alliance to Save Energy	Industry, policy makers, researchers
Batibouw	Industry
Berlin Green Investment Summit	Industry, policy makers, researchers
Building Greening	Industry, policy makers
Citizens Energy Forum	Policy makers, researchers
ecee summer study	Industry, policy makers
EE Global Forum	Industry, policy makers
Energy Efficiency Conference	Industry, policy makers, researchers
Energy Efficiency Finance Forum	Industry, policy makers
Energy Evaluation Europe	Industry, policy makers, researchers
Enlit Europe	Industry, policy makers, researchers
Euro Conferences (Association of European Operational Research Societies)	Industry, researchers
European Energy Efficiency Day	Industry, policy makers, researchers
European Sustainable Energy Week	Industry, policy makers, researchers
GreenBuild	Industry, policy makers
IISA	Industry, researchers,

<u>Impact Days RENOWAVE.AT</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>International Energy Forum on Advanced Building Skins</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>International PassivHouse Conference</u>	Industry, policy makers
<u>ISEC Conference</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>MIPIM</u>	Industry
<u>Mostra Convegno Expocomfort</u>	Industry, policy makers
<u>RECHARGE</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>REHVA Brussels Summit</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>Renovate Europe Days</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>Sustainable Places conference</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers
<u>Sustainable Energy Days</u>	Policy makers
<u>World Green Building Week</u>	Industry, policy makers
<u>World Sustainable Energy Days</u>	Industry, policy makers, researchers

8. Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters

8.1. Synergies with other relevant EU initiatives: Smart Energy Cluster

Science is, by nature, a compound work. Despite focusing on original initiatives, ENERGATE builds on knowledge produced by other projects – and it is also expected to inspire and support other research projects by providing inputs and information.

This exchange is only possible when synergies are in place: ENERGATE has been already started communications regularly with other projects (EN-TRACK, BIGG, MODERATE, InEExS, MATRYCS, BD4NRGY, I-ENERGY, Fortesie, DigiBUILD, DEDALUS, Enpower, Crete Valley, Hedge-IoT, METABUILD) and partnered with them in joint activities, so to build a win-win scenario where all projects increase their reach, all receive valuable inputs, and all have the opportunity to frame their work within the work being carried out by others.

As a starting point, a preliminary list of relevant projects has already been laid out, as seen in D7.2. These projects were chosen because they either gather a community that includes ENERGATE target stakeholders, or they are carrying / have carried out research that can be of value to the ENERGATE work.

After the preliminary list, ENERGATE has managed to bring EU funded projects together under the Smart Energy Cluster. The cluster especially engages all projects for common communication activities. Moreover, from a technical point of view, a file has been shared on TEAMS Sharepoint to monitor the technical dissemination discussion with other EU funded projects. A more detailed overview of the cluster and of all other synergies will be laid out in D6.5 (Joint activities with other projects and initiatives -V1).

The target KPI set for this segment has been achieved. However, the high impact of this task makes it worthy to set a stretch goal. A new target of 2 more clustering activities until the end of the project will be set.

9. Communication and Dissemination activities: reporting methodology (KPIs and monitoring)

A [Communication & Dissemination monitoring tool](#) have been created at project's start. All partners will be responsible to report their activities during the overall duration of ENERGATE

Table 4: ENERGATE communication tools and planning

Communication Tool	Time / Frequency	Monitoring Measure
Project Identity	M2	NA
ENERGATE Website	M5 / At least 5,000 unique visitors of & 15% return visitors	Website statistics (Google Analytics)
Dedicated project page on the beneficiaries' website	M5	NA
Social Media	During the project implementation / At least 30 announcements, reports' posts, etc. in partners' and relevant sites and platforms	All social networks have their own monitoring tools
Newsletters	1-2/year sent to people registered on the ENERGATE website	Newsletter's tool report, including openings, clicks & list of recipients
Brochure	M5 / 200 downloads per year	Number of downloads on the website, number of copies distributed & were tracked
One pager	Events distribution and online presentation	List of events where exposed, photos & list of participants, number of downloads on the website
Infographics and factsheet	WP2 reports, financing typologies, platform, presenting the pilots from WP4, etc.	Number of downloads on the website, number of copies distributed & were tracked
Scientific Papers	All along project duration / At least 2 papers submitted to scientific journals or to a Special Issue, at least 2 conference papers	Number of papers submitted
Media pieces	During the project implementation / 3 articles or press releases per partner, readership expected: 1000 people / At least 10 references, articles and mentions in relevant communications and media	Media monitoring performed regularly. Copies will be shared on our website.
Clustering activities	Clustering via website, social media and joint development of activities	Monitoring of publications (analytics) and meetings (lists)

Communication Tool	Time / Frequency	Monitoring Measure
Events	Webinars, 4 Regional Training Workshops (in Latvia Spain, Italy, Hungary), EU final event in Brussels	Agenda, Participants' lists

9.1. Stretch goals for next period

In line with the strategy updates referred in the previous paragraphs, some stretch goals were added to the communication and dissemination of ENERATE:

Table 5: Updated list of KPI

Activity	KPI	Stretch goal
Social media	30 posts	238 posts
Newsletter	5 newsletters	5 own newsletters
		2 external references
Infographics and fact sheets	Assets for WP2 reports	3
Scientific papers	2 papers	3 more scientific publications
	2 conference papers	
	10 references in relevant media	5 more
Clustering activities	Joint development of at least one activity	2 activities

10. Planned activities

In this section, we provide an overview of the planned communication & dissemination activities for the upcoming year of the project as well as the communication activities already conducted until M3. Partners have identified relevant events, workshops and other communication activities relevant for the project. In the next update of this deliverable, we will provide an overview of all communication and dissemination activities that will have been done until the end of the project implementation.

Table 6: ENERGATE planned events from M16-M30

Time Period	Partner	Activity Title	Target Group (s)	Related task
M16- M30	ALL	Regional Workshops in pilot countries (1 already occurred in Madrid 2023) - Riga (May 2024), Hungary (April 2025), Italy (November 2024)	Local stakeholders, government officials, industry experts, and local building owners/managers, financiers in the respective pilot countries	T5.3 Regional Training Workshops
M16-M30	Pilot Partners	10 stakeholders' webinars in pilot countries (2x Pilot partners)	Pilot partners, local stakeholders, policymakers, and industry experts in the pilot countries	T.5.2 Stakeholder Consultations
M16-M30	ALL	Standardisation Events	regulators involved in creating and implementing standards in energy efficiency and building sectors, Industry professionals	T.6.2 Standardisation Clustering and joint activities with EU funded projects / initiatives
M17	NTUA	EMCEI 2024 Andreoulaki, I., Papapostolou, A., Kotrogiannis, V., Marinakis, V. (2024, May). Promoting retrofitting projects in buildings: the designing steps of an online marketplace. In 2024 6 th Euro-Mediterranean Conference for Environmental Integration (EMCEI)	Environmental scientists, engineers, and researchers in environmental and materials science	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters
M17	IEECP, NTUA	Participation to Sustainable Energy Days (Organisation of a joint event with -InEEExS-FORTESIE "From Tech to Transformation:	Stakeholders involved in sustainable energy, building	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination,

Time Period	Partner	Activity Title	Target Group (s)	Related task
		Accelerating Building Energy Efficiency through ICT Solution")	renovation, and energy efficiency project, blockchain technology and ICT solutions	and networking boosters T6.2 Standardisation Clustering and joint activities with EU funded projects / initiatives
M17	REHVA	ENERGATEs' participation at BuiltHub Final Event	Building industry professionals, EU official, data scientists and IT professionals, Research and academic institutions, Investors and financial institutions, Environmental NGOs	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters
M18-M19	NTUA	Paper presentation in EURO Conference 2024 Papapostolou, A., Andreoulaki, I., Kotrogiannis, V., Marinakis, V. (2024, June – July). Utilising Decision-Making methods and online tools to accelerate sustainable renovation investments: Insights from a stakeholder engagement approach. In <i>2024 33rd EURO Conference</i>	Operations researchers, economists, and stakeholders from energy sector	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters
M19	NTUA	Paper presentation in IISA 2024 conference Tentative paper title: A decision support tool for aggregation and prioritisation of energy efficiency investments in buildings.	Academics, industry researchers, policymakers, and professionals interested in intelligent systems applications for sustainable energy	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters
M22	ESC, IEECP, NTUA, REHVA	Participation in ENLIT conference	Energy sector professionals, technology developers, and	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination,

Time Period	Partner	Activity Title	Target Group (s)	Related task
			policymakers involved in the energy transition.	and networking boosters
M23	IEECP, NTUA, REHVA	REHVA Brussels Summit	Researchers and academics, HVAC professionals, building engineers, financiers, architects and general public	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters
M27	NTUA	EMAN Conference 2025	Professionals and academics in environmental and sustainability management, stakeholders engaged in the energy sector	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters
M27	ESC, IEECP, NTUA, REHVA	MIPIM 2025	Real estate professionals, investors, architects, and city planners involved in international property markets	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters
M28-M30	IEECP, NTUA, REHVA	Organisation of final event in Brussels	Project partners, EU officials, industry leaders, and stakeholders interested in the project outcomes and future of energy efficiency financing in buildings	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters

Table 7: ENERGATE planned communication resources from M16-M30

Time Period	Partner	Activity Title	Target Group (s)	Related task
M17	IEECP	Update communication material (poster, brochure) with the updated LIFE KPIs.	General Public, stakeholders from the energy and financing, sector,	T7.3 Communication package of Tools and material

Time Period	Partner	Activity Title	Target Group (s)	Related task
			ENERGATE partners	
M16-M30	ALL	ENERGATE Project promotion in all partners websites	Existing and potential project partners, stakeholders in the energy efficiency financing.	T.7.2 Digital outreach
M16-M30	NTUA	New scientific publications (5 more according to new stretch goals)	Academic researchers, policy makers, industry professionals involved in energy efficiency and sustainable building practices.	T7.2 Digital Outreach
M16-M30	NTUA	ENERGATE New Press Releases to further promote planned events (table 6)	Stakeholders in the energy and financing sector	T.7.2 Digital outreach
M16-M30	REHVA	Liasing and participating in relevant discussions with standardisation bodies	Standardisation bodies, regulatory agencies, and professionals in standards development for energy efficiency	T.6.2 Standardisation Clustering and joint activities with EU funded projects / initiatives
M16-M30	NTUA, IEECP	ENERGATE Factsheets on Pilot Typologies for dissemination and communication of events	Participants of the events, stakeholders in the energy and financing sector	T7.3 Communication package of Tools and material
M16-M30	NTUA, IEECP	ENERGATE Infographics for dissemination and communication of events, surveys	Participants of the events, stakeholders in the energy and financing sector	T7.3 Communication package of Tools and material
M16-M30	NTUA	Events-News-Blog Items published on ENERGATE Website	Website visitors, including industry professionals, potential collaborators, and public interested in energy efficiency updates	T.7.2 Digital outreach

Time Period	Partner	Activity Title	Target Group (s)	Related task
M16-M30	ALL	3 Articles per Partner (3x12) 36 in total	Website visitors, including industry professionals, potential collaborators, and public interested in energy efficiency updates	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters
M16-M30	NTUA	Dissemination of the public deliverables	General public, policymakers, academic and research institutions	T.7.2 Digital outreach
M16-M30	ALL	Joint Activities (Dissemination and events) within the #SmartEnergyCluster	Partners from #SmartEnergyCluster, energy efficiency stakeholders	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters
M16-M30	ALL	Join Activities (Dissemination and events) with EU projects outside the #SmartEnergyCluster	Participants from other EU projects, energy efficiency stakeholders	T.7.4 Communication, dissemination, and networking boosters
M16-M30	NTUA, IEECP	Preparation of Communication packages for the planned events and results	General Public, stakeholders from the energy and financing sector, ENERGATE partners	T7.3 Communication package of Tools and material
M16-M30	NTUA	Social Media posts (YouTube, LinkedIn, X) to further promote ENERGATEs' activities and platform	General public interested in energy efficiency, finance and sustainable energy solutions	T.7.2 Digital outreach
M18	NTUA	ENERGATE promotional (animation) video	General public, potential investors, and stakeholders from the energy and financing sector	T.7.2 Digital outreach
M19	IEECP	Communication campaign for platform roll out including social media posts, website announcements, articles, press releases etc.	Building owners, implementors, investors, and public bodies interested in	T7.3 Communication package of Tools and material

Time Period	Partner	Activity Title	Target Group (s)	Related task
			energy efficiency projects.	

ANNEX I- Logo selection process

Before the kick-off meeting, NTUA and REHVA worked on eight different logo propositions to be presented during the kick-off to all partners. Partners have then been asked to select their favourite option via a google form (<https://forms.gle/sEqKaVnWnkdmilYj6>).

ENERGATE LOGO

Which logo better represents ENERGATE?

reihvahvac@gmail.com (not shared) [Switch account](#)

Option 1

Option 1

Option 5

Option 5

Option 2

Option 2

Option 6

Option 6

Option 3

Option 3

Option 7

Option 7

Option 4

Option 4

Option 8

Option 8

ANNEX II- ENERGATE Brand Manual

The ENERGATE brand manual is available in the project repository and can be consulted [here](#).

OUR TEAM

Project Coordinator

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